

Data Management Plan

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Document Overview

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About the project

Cities concentrate high density socio-economic activities, consuming 70% of global resources, producing 60-80% of anthropogenic greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and generating waste of resources, energy and water. This is a critical issue, but at the same time it offers opportunities.

Circular economy models can reduce this waste and reduce human environmental impacts.

Eclectic brings circular economy from theory to action in cities, by improving the understanding of cities as complex multi-level ecosystems with inputs, outputs, and resource flows. The project designs, implements, and monitors strategic action plans for circular economy in cities, taking care to address vulnerable groups and to reduce inequality in selecting circular models.

Four city-region living labs (CiRLabs) located in Italy, Lithuania, Sweden and Portugal will be the testing sites where the circular practices will be implemented. In the CiRLabs, stakeholder engagement processes will be the means to identify needs and visions for CE, and to select CE actions that fit them. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) will be defined to measure and monitor the effectiveness of the selected circular economy action plans.

Outputs from the project will include four scientific papers, three reports, four actionable reports, a toolbox, workshops, and trainings.

Project partners

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the Data Management Plan of the Eclectic project. The Data Management Plan is a living document which details the life-cycle management of the data within the project Eclectic, including data collection, processing and/or generation. It aims to ensure that research data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR).

The DMP addresses the type of data to be collected, processed and generated throughout the project and how these data will be collected, processed and/or generated. It describes the methodologies and standards to be applied across the data management life cycle, and the strategies for promoting data exploitation, including consideration for sharing and/or making data accessible in open access formats for reuse and replication.

It also details provisions for the maintenance, preservation and curation of data during and after the project's conclusion. This DPM is designed to uphold the principles of ensuring that research data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR), thereby facilitating effective utilization and dissemination of project findings. Finally, financial, security, and ethical considerations have been integrated into the plan to ensure comprehensive management and responsible handling of project data.

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Term	Description
BIA	Bolzano Institutional Archive
CiRLab	City-Region Living Lab
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DOC	Miscrosoft Word processing document file format
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DMP	Data Management Plan
DUT	Driving Urban Transitions Partnership
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
H2020	Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
HBS	Household budget survey
HTTP	HyperText Transfer Protocol
INE	Instituto Nacional de Estadística
ISTAT	Istituto Nazionale di Statistica
JPG	Joint Photographics (Experts) Group
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LCA	Life-Cycle Assessment
MFA	Material Flow Accounting
NUTS	Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics
ORD	Open Research Data
PDF	Portable Document Format
TIF	Tagged Image (File) Format
TXT	Text file
UM	Urban Metabolism
WP	Work Package
XLS	Microsoft Excel spreadsheet file format

1 Introduction

This Data Management Plan provides a comprehensive overview of the various aspects involved in handling project data, from its collection and storage to ensuring its Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability (FAIR).

Through structured chapters, it investigates the types of data collected, the methods used to process data (Chapters 2 and 3) and the principles for making data retrievable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR) (Chapter 4). Furthermore, the costs associated with collecting, storing and publishing data and the related security measures required to safeguard data integrity and comply with the provisions of the GDPR are analysed (chapters 5 and 6). Finally, the ethical aspects of research are considered in Chapter 7.

This DMP builds on the Horizon Europe Data Management Plan Template and on the DMP of the project Artemis. The DMP of the Eclectic project is structured to align with the Artemis project's approach to data analysis within the circular economy domain. This alignment results from the shared thematic focus and methodologies between the two projects. It is important to clarify that the Eclectic DMP, while taking its basis from the Artemis framework, represents an independent and comprehensive effort by the Eclectic research team. This document outlines the unique contributions and methodologies employed by Eclectic, while acknowledging the valuable groundwork done by the Artemis project¹.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) is fundamental for effective research data management, evolving alongside the project's development. It serves as a dynamic document, continuously expanding in detail and specificity as the project advances. Consequently, regular revisions and updates are essential to incorporate new insights, account for changes in data availability and collection methods, and adapt to evolving collaborative frameworks. Each update will be accompanied by a revised version number and timetable to maintain clarity and accountability throughout the project lifecycle.

¹ For more information about the DMP of ARTEMIS (10.5281/zenodo.6278561), please visit: <https://zenodo.org/records/6278561>.

Artemis has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 101026073.

2 Data summary

This section summarizes the types of data that will be collected, processed and/or generated, framed under the project objectives and research activities. It describes the data sources, data storage, access, use and reuse of data from a range of sources, as well as expected data formats and estimated space requirements (data size).

The data collection, analysis, processing, and generation within Eclectic are directly linked to and are required to fulfil the five project's specific objectives, each of which is addressed in a work package (WP), as outlined in the project proposal:

- WP1. to establish the analytical tools (Urban Metabolism – Life Cycle Assessment UM-LCA) needed to describe resource use and associated environmental impacts in the four city-region living labs (CiRLabs); to model future circular economy (CE) strategy scenarios and assess their potential to contribute to environmental targets; to address matters of space and place (where materials circulate), and potential unbalances & hotspots in the use of resources and environmental impacts; to track progress and monitor CE action plans via specific Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).
- WP2. to activate city-region living labs (CiRLabs) including stakeholder engagement processes for developing CE strategies with a focus on entrepreneurial discovery process (EDP) to engage SMEs, businesses, and entrepreneurs in exploring circular & shared solutions.
- WP3. to develop and apply a framework to map socio-economic, cultural, demographic, and relational factors that influence household consumption and circularity choices in CiRLabs, to design and implement just & inclusive CE strategies.
- WP4. to communicate and disseminate information on the project and related activities, events, and outcomes among a wide range of stakeholders and at a broader society level; to provide educational and training materials on the project and on just & inclusive circular city-regions; to promote the replication of the project outputs in other cities.
- WP5. To establish an efficient management process that guarantees the achievement of the project objectives as planned in the proposal.

2.1 Data collection: purpose, types, and relation to research activities

In Eclectic, data collection will take place in WP1, WP2 and WP3. WP1 and WP2 will mainly re-use existing data (e.g. statistical) while WP3 will also generate new data (e.g. interviews).

The data collection will take place mainly during the first 24 months of the project, and it will include:

- statistical data at (i) international, national, regional and local (municipal) scales, which will be used to characterize material and product flows and to develop the material flow accounting (MFA) model, within the UM-LCA framework; (ii) at regional and municipal level for the characterization of the CiRLabs; (iii) microdata from household budget surveys at national, regional and municipal level to map the factors influencing household consumption toward circular economy.
- technical and scientific literature data on product's material composition, lifespan, life-cycle stages and processes, among others, which will be used to complement statistical data to model and characterize the product flows and respective life-cycles within the UM-LCA framework; technical and scientific literature at regional and municipal level for the characterization of the CiRLabs; technical and scientific literature at national, regional and municipal level for the mapping of circular economy strategies.
- qualitative data from interviews, surveys and workshops that will be generated in WP3, to map socio-economic, cultural, demographic, and relational factors influencing household consumption and consumption behaviour.

The content, sources, storage, and formats of the types of data collected are described in the next sub-chapters.

2.1.1 Statistical data

Statistical data are quantitative information collected and organized from a sample of population. In Eclectic, statistical data will be collected and analysed in WP1 for the modelling of the UM-LCA in the four CiRLabs, in WP2 for the characterisation of the CiRLabs and in WP3 for the analysis of factors influencing household consumption. In this latter case, microdata from national household budget surveys will be used for each country.

The main data sources include public and online available databases of international statistics (Eurostat), national statistics organisation in Italy (ISTAT), Portugal (INE), Lithuania (OSP) and Sweden (SCB), and local statistics offices such as ASTAT (Province of Bolzano).

Databases used and access conditions are listed in Table 1. The list is not exhaustive and will be update during the project.

Table 1: Statistical data sources in Italy, Portugal, Lithuania and Sweden

Country	WP	Source	Licensing and access	Level	Type of data
Italy	WP1, WP2	Online database ISTAT – Istituto Nazionale di Statistica (national statistics office in Italy) https://www.istat.it/en/	Data and analysis from ISTAT are licensed under Creative Commons version 4.0 Deed: they can be copied, redistribute, transmitted and freely adapted, even for commercial use, provided appropriate credit (attribution). Additional information: https://www.istat.it/en/legal-notice	National	Macrodata
	WP3	Household budget survey (HBS) – ISTAT	The use of the microdata from the HBS is possible under a specific confidential and management protocol. (See HBS).	National	Microdata - Scientific use Files (SUFs)
	WP1, WP2, WP3	Online database ASTAT (regional statistics office in the Province of Bolzano) https://astat.provincia.bz.it/it/default.asp	Dissemination and use of data, information, tables and graphs, including partial or total reproduction of the content of publications and pages, authorised only with citation of the source.	Regional	Macrodata

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Portugal	WP1, WP2 , WP3	Online database INE – Instituto Nacional de Estatística (national statistics office in Portugal) https://www.ine.pt/	The statistical data made available can be used and reused by the users in accordance with the Creative Commons CC BY Attribution 4.0 license provided that the source is acknowledged, as follows: Source: Instituto Nacional de Estatística (INE) – Portugal (identification of the statistical information mentioned; reference period of the information). Users may download or copy documents for personal or commercial use, but Statistics Portugal shall continue to own the respective copyright. Should the user modify the original data, it must be explicitly mentioned.	National	Macrodata
	WP3	Household budget survey (HBS) - INE	The use of the microdata from the HBS is possible under a specific confidential and management protocol. (See HBS).	National	Microdata - Scientific use Files (SUFs)
Lithuania	WP1, WP2	Online database OSP – Official Statistics Portal, provided by the State Data Agency https://osp.stat.gov.lt/pradinis	Data and analysis form OSP are licensed under Creative Commons version 4.0 Deed: they can be copied, redistribute, transmitted and freely adapted, even for commercial use, provided appropriate credit (attribution).	National	Macrodata
	WP3	Household budget survey (HBS) – OSP The data is provided by Open Data sets, https://open-data-sets-ls-osp-sdg.hub.arcgis.com/	The microdata from the HBS in Lithuania are open sources and available online. (See HBS). https://osp.stat.gov.lt/documents/10180/5118910/Nam%C5%B3+%C5%ABki%C5%B3+biud%C5%BEet%C5%B3+tyrimas+%5BEN%5D+517.html#row-37	National	Microdata

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Sweden	WP1, WP2	Online database Statistikmyndigheten (SCB) (national statistics office in Sweden) https://www.scb.se/	Statistics Sweden uses the standardised license Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY 4.0). This means that you are free to copy, reproduce, and redistribute all statistics (including tables, figures and infographics) on Statistics Sweden's website. However, when you use or disseminate statistics from scb.se, you must always state Statistics Sweden as the source ("Source: Statistics Sweden").	National	Macrodata
	WP3	Household budget survey (HBS) – SCB	The use of the microdata from the HBS is possible under a specific confidential and management protocol. (See HBS).	National	Microdata - Scientific use Files (SUFs)

Statistical data will be mostly collected in CSV and XLS formats, in cases, PDF files may also be used to collect smaller amounts of data, which will be manually transferred or integrated into CSV files. Statistical raw data collected is expected to not exceed 40G.

2.1.1.1 Household budget survey (HBSs)

Household budget surveys (HBSs) are national surveys focusing mainly on household expenditure on goods and services. Their main aim (especially at national level) is to calculate weights for the consumer price index.

For more information regarding the **Household budget survey** visit:

<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/microdata/household-budget-survey>

Since the survey is conducted based on a gentleman's agreement, each EU country decides the objectives, methodology, and frequency of the survey. Although there have been continuous efforts to make the data comparable across countries and over time, differences remain. The surveys vary between countries in terms of frequency, timing, content or structure. To access the microdata of the household budget survey for each country it is necessary to fulfil specific protocols. Table 2, Table 3, Table 4, and Table 5 summarize the main information concerning the household budget surveys that will be collected and used for the four CiRLabs.

Table 2: Household budget survey information for Italy

ITALY

The HBS in Italy is conducted annually by ISTAT in the framework of the National Statistics Programme, the document that rules the production of official statistical information.

The focus of the HBS is represented by all expenditures incurred by resident households to purchase goods and services exclusively devoted to household consumption (self-consumptions, imputed rentals and presents are included); every other expenditure for a different purpose is excluded from the data collection (e. g., payments of fees and business expenditures).

For more information visit: <https://www.istat.it/en/archivio/180353>

To access the microdata of the HBS, a request was submitted to the ISTAT contact center for the Scientific Use Files (SUFs) related to the HBS. SUFs are microdata files, with no direct identifiers, which have been subject to control methods to protect confidentiality.

To success the request a Principal researcher should submit a research proposal, a confidentiality declaration, a confidentiality declaration of individual researchers involved in the project and additional certification in case of joint projects. In the case of Eclectic, a request was submitted by Dr. Chiara Pellegrini (Eurac Research - Principal researcher) to access the HBS's microdata for years 2015, 2016, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020 and 2021.

The other researcher involved in project with access to this microdata are Dr. Jessica Balest (Eurac Research), Dr. Silvia Tomasi (Eurac Research), Dr. Nicolas Caballero (Eurac Research). They have signed individual statements with the data management and confidentiality requirements. The access to SUFs is free of charge. For more information visit: [Microdata files \(istat.it\)](#)

SUFs will be kept in a classified folder with limited access protected by a password to the researchers listed above within Eurac Research's servers. The expected date of access to these data is 01/07/2024 and they will be kept until 22/08/2025, after which they will be destroyed.

Table 3: Household budget survey information for Portugal

PORTUGAL

The HBS in Portugal is carried out every five years by INE. It collects data on the income and expenditures of households. The classification and coding of consumption expenditure uses the International Classification of Individual Consumption by Purpose (COICOP).

To access the microdata of the HBS, a request needs to be submitted to the e Direção Geral de Estatísticas da Educação e Ciência (DGEEC) for the Scientific Use Files (SUFs) related to the HBS. All datasets are anonymized and include no personal or sensitive details.

The request should include an accreditation request form, a declaration of commitment and GDPR Privacy notice and consent.

For the access to these data, a request will be submitted by Dr. Rita Garcia (University of Coimbra). Other researcher with access to these data are Dr. Nicolas Caballero (Eurac Research), Dr. Jessica Balest (Eurac Research), Dr. Silvia Tomasi (Eurac Research), Dr. Chiara Pellegrini (Eurac Research), Federico Voltolini (Eurac Research), Riccardo Fraboni (Eurac Research), Leonardo Rosado (Chalmers University). They have signed individual statements with the data management and confidentiality requirements.

The access to SUFs is free of charge.

For more information visit:

https://www.ine.pt/xportal/xmain?xpid=INE&xpgid=ine_serv_clientes&INST=161301979&ine_smenu.boui=161303032&ine_smenu.selected=161303243&xlang=en

INE's statistical microdata will be stored locally and shared physically, such as on CDs, USB, to adhere to protocol requirements.

The expected date of access to these data is 01/07/2024 and they will be kept until 01/11/2028, after which they will be destroyed.

Table 4: Household budget survey information for Lithuania

LITHUANIA

The HBS in Lithuania is conducted every four years by OSP. The objective of the survey is to estimate household consumption expenditure and its structure in various household groups by place of residence, main source and level of income, household composition, educational attainment, and age of the household head.

The structure of consumption expenditure is used for calculating the macroeconomic

indicators. The first HBS was conducted in Lithuania in 2003 and until 2008, it was annually. Since 2009 the time frequency raised to 4–5 years (2012, 2016, 2021). For more information visit: <https://osp.stat.gov.lt/documents/10180/5118910/Nam%C5%B3+%C5%ABki%C5%B3+biud%C5%B Eet%C5%B3+tyrimas+%5BEN%5D+517.html>

Lithuanian microdata on Household Budget Survey are open sources and available online. For more information visit: <https://open-data-sets-ls-osp-sdg.hub.arcgis.com/pages/097fc7ed27b347c8bda3b973c19896ba>

Microdata will be kept in a folder in the shared OneDrive between partners. The date of access to these data is 01/03/2024 and they will be kept for a period not exceeding 5 years from the end of the project (2029), after which they will be destroyed.

Table 5: Household budget survey information for Sweden

SWEDEN

The statistics cover expenditures in different household groups and how expenditures are distributed among different goods and services. One of the most important tasks of statistics is to discover and highlight groups that are vulnerable in some respect. The survey has been carried out since 1958.

For more information visit: <https://www.scb.se/en/finding-statistics/statistics-by-subject-area/household-finances/household-expenditures/household-budget-survey-hbs/>

Statistics Sweden's microdata on individuals and enterprises is covered by secrecy, but you can access anonymised microdata following a confidentiality assessment, provided that Statistics Sweden considers that you have the grounds to process the data. To process your order and conduct a confidentiality assessment, Statistics Sweden needs the following documents:

- A specification of the microdata requested from Statistics Sweden, including a description of the population, register and variables involved.
- Research plan/Project plan.
- An application for ethical review and an approval decision (only applies to research purposes that include sensitive personal data under the GDPR).

For the access to these data a request was submitted by Dr. Leonardo Rosado (Chalmers University). He has signed individual statements with the data management and confidentiality requirements.

A cost for the access of the SUFs is expected but not yet known.

For more information visit: <https://www.scb.se/en/services/ordering-data-and-statistics/ordering-microdata/>

SUFs will be kept in the servers of the SCB.

2.1.2 Technical and scientific literature data

Technical and scientific literature data will be collected based on scientific journal articles, technical reports and life-cycle inventory datasets/databases, such as Ecoinvent² is protected by the End User Licence Agreement (EULA)³, which imposes restrictions on reproducing, sharing, or publicly displaying substantial portions of the database or its datasets. Scientific literature will be collected through the main journal articles databases such as SCOPUS, Google Scholar and Web of Science.

Technical and scientific literature will be kept in the partner's institutions servers. In the case of data protected by confidentiality licences, they will be kept in special folders with restricted access.

Data in text format will be collected in PDF or DOC files, while life cycle inventory data will be in XLS or CSV format, or in PDF. These files will later be manually converted or embedded into CSV files. The expected size of the technical and scientific literature data should not exceed 2 GB.

2.1.3 Interviews, surveys and workshops

Data from interviews, survey, and workshops will be generated as part of WP3. The data collected will be the basis for the qualitative analyses in Eclectic aimed at addressing the social inclusion objectives of the project.

- **Interviews**

Interviews will be conducted with local stakeholders, targeting local associations working with vulnerable groups and local authorities representing the CiRLabs. In the first case, the interviews will be used to investigate how different CE initiatives and strategies can benefit vulnerable groups, increasing their access to goods, services, and resources in city-regions. In the second case, the interviews will investigate the state of the art of CE in the CiRLabs, focusing on the objectives, priorities, vision, and aspiration of local authorities in relation to CE action plans.

Interviews will be conducted with citizens, and more specifically, with citizens that are consider vulnerable (such as migrants, low-income families, homeless). Contact to vulnerable citizens will be asked through the local associations and NGOs that will be involved during the Eclectic project. Given the sensitiveness of vulnerable target groups, a specific interview protocol will be followed and special care will be paid to privacy and data treatment. Each interviewee will be asked explicit written consent for the interview, allowing for the possibility to decline at each stage of the interview process. The principle remains that the interviewee is free to decline the

² [ecoinvent - Data with purpose.](#)

³ [EULA_new_branding_08_11_2023.pdf \(ecoinvent.org\)](#)

interview at any time, even when the local association or NGO has provided access to the interviewee.

The interviews will be recorded and transcribed. The recording will be stored in a classified folder with limited access on Eurac Research's servers that will be protected by a password. All the recordings will be destroyed at the end of the research project. Transcriptions will be classified in "original" and "anonymised" formats. Original transcriptions will be complete transcriptions, that will include personal data of the interviewee (e.g name and surname). Original transcriptions will be kept in a password-protected folder with limited access on Eurac Research's servers and will be destroyed at the end of the project. Anonymised transcriptions will be transcriptions without personal data. These transcriptions will be kept in a folder accessible to the project partners until the end of the project. After that, this data will be stored in a folder in the Eclectic's Zenodo Community in order to ensure the replicability.

The interviewees will be requested to fill-in and sign a consent form to acquire the consensus for the collection of personal data and the recording of the interviews in order to meet the European GDPR legislation (n. 2016/679)⁴. These documents will be kept for the time strictly necessary to achieve the purposes indicated, or for a period of time not exceeding 5 years from the end of the project (2030) in a password-protected folder with limited access on Eurac Research's servers.

The data quality is ensured through detailed notes taken after the interview by the interviewer and through a validation of the information and results from the qualitative analysis of the interviews. To ensure the quality of transcription a *naturalized transcription* [1] type will be adopted. This type of transcription adapts the oral language to the formal written language.

Interviews will be collected in audio format such as MPEG-4. The transcriptions in PDF or DOC files. The expected size of the interviews data should not exceed 6 GB.

- **Surveys**

In task 3.2, an anonymous survey will be designed by the project partners and distributed to a sample of citizens to explore the connections of socio-economic and cultural indicators with the willingness to share and consumption habits, and to understand how much sharing and circularity can connect to well-being. The data collected will be stored in a classified folder with limited access on Eurac Research's servers.

The survey will not collect data that allow direct identification of the person, and the collection and analysis procedures will be carried out in full compliance with European GDPR legislation (n. 2016/679).

Survey will be collected via online forms or on paper. In the first case, the software SurveyMonkey⁵ will be used. The choice to use this specific software is dictated by the fact that Eurac Research has a user licence for the software that ensures both privacy protection, ownership of the data to Eurac Research and back up in case of loss.

⁴ Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)

⁵ <https://uk.surveymonkey.com/>

In the second case, the surveys will be stored in special cabinets with restricted access in the offices of the partners involved in data collection. These data will then be digitally transformed to allow the complete analysis of the collected data. The paper version of the survey will be destroyed after the process of digitalisation.

The template of the online survey might be published in the Eclectic's Zenodo Community in order to ensure the replicability of the activity. While the data collected through the surveys will be published in aggregate form in Eclectic's Zenodo Community, deliverables or scientific articles.

Surveys will be collected in XLS, CSV or SPSS. The expected size of the survey data should not exceed 2 GB.

- **Stakeholder engagement and workshops**

Six workshops will be organised in each CiRLabs during the project. The workshops aim to collect data on best practices on CE and to initiate a dialogue between local stakeholders.

The organisation of the workshops involves a first stage of data collection through the mapping of local stakeholders in each CiRLabs. The mapping methodology will be developed by IPC - Instituto Politécnico de Coimbra and Eurac Research. An Excel file will be created for each CiRLabs for the collection of the information of the local stakeholders. For each stakeholder, partners will be asked to fill in fields with information such as: name of the organisation, contact person, field etc. None of these categories are 'sensitive categories of personal data'⁶. The final methodology to stakeholder mapping will be published in the Deliverable 2.1.

The completed excels file (file with the list of stakeholders) will not be public and it will be locally stored in the servers of each partner and will be kept for a period not exceeding 5 years from the end of the project (2030), after which they will be destroyed.

During the workshops data will be collected to catch the discussions of the participants. Data collected could consist in post-it, posters, notes. These materials will be digitally transformed through photography and scanning and stored in appropriate folders in the servers of the project partners. Digital data will be kept for up to five years at the end of the project, after which they will be destroyed. The original data collected (post-it, posters, notes) will be stored in appropriate cabinets with limited access in the partner's offices until the end of the project, after that they will be destroyed.

Photos may also be taken during the workshops for dissemination purposes. In this case explicit consent will be sought from the participants to meet the provisions of the GDPR.

⁶ Article 4(13), (14) and (15) and Article 9 and Recitals (51) to (56) of the GDPR

The following personal data is considered 'sensitive' and is subject to specific processing conditions:

personal data revealing racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs; trade-union membership; genetic data, biometric data processed solely to identify a human being; health-related data; data concerning a person's sex life or sexual orientation.

https://commission.europa.eu/law/law-topic/data-protection/reform/rules-business-and-organisations/legal-grounds-processing-data/sensitive-data/what-personal-data-considered-sensitive_en

Stakeholder mapping will be collected in XLS. The expected size of the stakeholder mapping should not exceed 2 GB.

While digital versions of post-it, posters, notes and photos will be collected in JPEG, PNG or PDF. The expected size of these documents should not exceed 3 GB.

2.2 Output of the project

The project will document its data collection, analysis, modelling, and findings through various scientific and technical outputs, including:

- Datasets used to characterize regional and urban material and product flows;
- Urban metabolism (MFA) modelling code, written in Python, inclusive of data analysis and processing;
- Modelling and results of life-cycle inventories;
- Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) addressing environmental sustainability in CiRLabs, along with recommendations and guidelines for their future application (presented in textual format);
- Code for the characterization of the household in base of the expenditures.
- Scientific publications, comprising technical reports, peer-reviewed articles in scientific journals, and conference papers.

The research aims to ensure maximum transparency, reproducibility and replicability of the data, code and the results generated. The selection of materials and methods was oriented to provide replicability and scalability. The research outcomes, data and results are intended to be usable beyond the project duration to support other projects on circular economy in other geographical areas and regional systems.

All scientific and technical outputs will be openly accessible, along with the necessary data for validation, provided that licensing, legal restrictions and access agreements permit. Exceptions may include data obtained from restricted or protected frameworks, such as scientific journal articles with limited access, Ecoinvent database/dataset and statistical microdata.

Source code files utilized for data analysis and processing within the UM-LCA modelling framework will be stored in a publicly accessible GitHub repository. A Git version control system will be employed to manage and accurately track data versioning. Furthermore, the model input and output datasets related to the UM-LCA framework, containing processed data and results concerning material and product flows, as well as life-cycle inventories, will be made openly available as open-data. These datasets will be accessible in Zenodo, stored in CSV format files, with detailed descriptions of column values and data formats provided in a TXT file. Additionally, metadata (including persistent identifiers) and data documentation will be furnished as ReadMe files.

A Zenodo community has been created for the project, which will be the repository for access to all datasets and documents: <https://zenodo.org/communities/eclectic>.

Figure 1: The Eclectic community in Zenodo

Datasets shared on both GitHub and Zenodo will adhere to the standard Data Package format supported by Frictionless Data—a format developed by the Open Knowledge Foundation (OKF). This format supports the organization and specification of metadata, including details such as title, description, sources, authors, license, dataset description, and column definitions, all encapsulated within a Data Package JSON file that is both human and machine readable.

Scientific results and textual data will be openly accessible in conventional formats such as DOC and PDF files, primarily for textual documents such as scientific journal articles, interviews, conference papers, presentations, and posters. Visualizations will be stored in standard binary file formats (raster images) such as TIF or JPG.

The total size of data processed and/or generated within the project, including source code files, datasets, and text-based scientific results, is estimated to be no more than 30 GB.

2.3 Data utility

The research data will be accessible to researchers and practitioners who are interested in improving the framework, refining the modelling code, or applying it to different case studies and datasets. In addition, experts and consultants working with public authorities, policymakers, and companies, can use project data and results to potentially apply them to different case studies, supporting decision-making processes related to the development and implementation of circular economy strategies, with a particular focus on vulnerable groups.

3 Handling project data: access, security, storage and back-up

The data shared between the partners will be stored in a shared OneDrive folder accessible only to authorised personnel involved in the research or execution of the project, including those of the partner institutions. Literature data, including scientific articles and technical reports, will be managed using Mendeley and/or Zotero software. Access to the project's webpage is restricted to authorized staff with specific permissions.

Eclectic will gather, process, and model data obtained from various researchers, experts, and organizations. All project outputs and processed data will be explicitly linked to their respective data inputs and sources. Proper citation and acknowledgment will be provided to recognize the original sources, authors, and data archives. This approach aims to ensure that future users of Eclectic outputs can easily locate and access the original data used.

For specific provisions on data access, security, storage and back-up refers to Chapter 2.

- **Data Documentation**

The data folders within the Eclectic project will be structured and organized according to the project's main structure and activities. Briefly, the following folders will be developed: General, WP1 – Impact assessment framework, WP2 – City Region Living Labs, WP3 – Just and inclusive CE, WP4 – Dissemination and Exploitation, and WP5 – Project Management.

To facilitate the findability of files and to standardize the structure of the folder and the file naming convention a ReadMe file that describes this information will be accessible in the General folder.

Each data file will have a descriptive and unique name to ensure consistency and facilitate access, as follows:

- Scientific and Technical Literature: First author's surname – year (yyyy) - short title/keywords.
- Statistical Datasets: keywords - source - geographic scale/spatial resolution – year; A ReadMe file will accompany datasets to provide related documentation, enhancing interpretation, accessibility, and reusability (further details in section).
- Text Files: Version date (ddmmyyyy) - short title – author – contributor of most recent changes.

4 Making data FAIR

This section outlines the strategies employed by Eclectic to promote the dissemination and exploitation of data and results in line with FAIR data principles, emphasizing data findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.

4.1 Ensuring Data Findability

Data collected, processed, and generated within Eclectic will be deposited in Zenodo whenever possible, ensuring compliance with access, use, and reproduction conditions stipulated by existing licenses, protocols, or agreements. Deposited data will be identifiable and locatable through a clear naming structure and standard identification mechanism, complemented by metadata to enhance discoverability. Zenodo's integration with the OpenAIRE portal further facilitates data findability.

4.1.1 Data Naming and References

Datasets and other scientific outputs deposited in public repositories will be named to reflect their content, incorporating the following elements:

- Project name
- DX.Y (Deliverable, if applicable)
- Product name (e.g., dataset or article short title)
- Version
- Date (e.g., storage date or publication year)

See the example: `ECLECTIC_D5.1_DataManagementPlan_v01_300424`

To enhance data discoverability, findability, identifiability, and traceability, each dataset and scientific output will have a corresponding record, such as:

- Quantitative Datasets: Identified by a unique Uniform Resource Locator (URL) provided by GitHub, ensuring accessibility via the GitHub web-platform.
- Scientific and technical outputs (e.g., journal articles): Assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for unique and persistent identification. Zenodo assigns a DOI to an object unless the object already has one. Additionally, Zenodo's metadata includes an alternate identifier field, enabling integration of other identifiers (e.g., GitHub URL) into the object's Zenodo metadata.

When appropriate, authors' persistent digital identifiers, such as ORCID, and ROR IDs for research performing organizations will be used, which are both integrated into the Zenodo platform. Clear version numbers will be included in all project reports, deliverables, datasets, and source code files to facilitate revisions, updates, and maintain easy identifiability and traceability.

4.1.2 Metadata

Metadata plays a crucial role in enhancing the readability, traceability, usability, and management of scientific outputs deposited in repositories. The chosen repositories for Eclectic's research data deposition, namely GitHub and Zenodo, offer structured fields to compile metadata. These fields typically include:

- Project title
- Document or scientific output title
- Names of authors and/or researchers involved
- Institutional affiliation
- Abstract or summary of the project and/or data
- Research topic or subject
- Publication or release date/year
- Geographic scope or coverage
- Instrumentation used
- Access policies, rights, restrictions, or licenses
- Language
- Tags or keywords
- Funding framework information

4.1.3 Keywords

Search keywords are essential for maximizing data findability, reusability, and exploitation. Keywords will encompass the project name (Eclectic) and topics relevant to the project, such as circular economy, environmental sustainability, urban metabolism, life-cycle assessment, material flow analysis, environmental impacts, vulnerable groups, among others. To harmonise the use of keywords within the project, a document with a shared definition of Eclectic keywords is being prepared.

4.2 Ensuring Open Data Accessibility

Eclectic embraces the principle of "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" Accordingly, most data collected, processed, and generated within the project will be deposited in open repositories, ensuring free access for all interested parties.

However, certain data may not be made publicly available due to existing licenses, agreements, protocols, or privacy issues. In such instances, the data source will be clearly identified, enabling potential users to locate and, if permissible, access the data. Some factors that might restrict open access to collected data include:

- Statistical Microdata, collected under confidentiality and data protection protocols or frameworks.

- Case Study Data, collected from the four CiRLabs under specific access agreements that may impose sharing or reproduction conditions.
- Life-Cycle Inventory Data, derived from databases like Ecoinvent, subject to user agreements that may limit data reproduction.
- Scientific Literature and Other Data, subject to restricted access or sharing conditions.
- Personal data collected through interviews, surveys, and workshops.

These restrictions are implemented to ensure compliance with data protection regulations and agreements while striving to maximize the openness and accessibility of project data wherever possible.

4.2.1 Data Deposition and Accessibility

Datasets collected, processed, and generated during the Eclectic project will be deposited on the Zenodo platform, adhering to any specified restrictions. These datasets will be saved in widely accepted file formats, such as XLS or CSV. Eclectic will comply with Zenodo's guidelines concerning data deposition, format, and size. Source code files developed within the project will be publicly deposited in GitHub repositories. GitHub offers unrestricted web browser access and supports bulk downloads through HTTP or git without authentication. Additionally, releasing the code on Zenodo will assign a DOI and full metadata, enhancing their discoverability through Zenodo, OpenAIRE, and other relevant platforms. Both Zenodo and GitHub repositories will remain accessible beyond the project's lifespan.

4.2.2 Publication and Archiving

Scientific peer-reviewed journal articles resulting from Eclectic's research will be published in Green or Gold Open Access. The final Version of Record will be archived in the Bolzano Institutional Archive (BIA), aligning with Eurac Research's Open Access Policy and with the open access policies of each partner. Public reports and conference proceedings will also be archived in BIA, an Institutional Open Access Repository compliant with FAIR data principles, and Zenodo.

4.2.3 Accessibility and Documentation

All deposited datasets, source code files, and scientific outputs will be linked on Eurac's project webpage www.eurac.edu/eclectic that has been jointly agreed by the Consortium to be the main project website. ReadMe files accompanying datasets will contain relevant documentation to facilitate interpretation, accessibility, and reuse (see section 4.4 for further details). Text-based scientific outputs will be available in standard formats like DOC and PDF, leveraging widely accessible free software tools. No data access committee is anticipated, streamlining the accessibility process for users.

4.3 Ensuring Data Interoperability

Eclectic, as an interdisciplinary research project, operates within a context where no established standards exist for depositing the type of research data and scientific outputs it will generate. To enhance interoperability, Eclectic will adopt standards relevant to statistical datasets, such as international classification systems for economic activities, products, and materials. Additionally, the project will draw from existing projects in similar fields, relevant metadata schemes provided by selected repositories (e.g., Zenodo), and adhere to the OpenAIRE guidelines.

File formats will be chosen to maximize accessibility, ensuring compatibility with commonly available softwares.

4.4 Promoting Data Re-use

Datasets will be made accessible via Zenodo, utilizing the Data Package format. This format prioritizes focus, web accessibility, distribution, openness, integration with existing tools, and simplicity. Each dataset will be published as a standalone Git repository, adhering to the technical specifications of the Data Package format. The repository will include:

- A ReadMe file detailing the dataset's title, content description, materials, methods used for data processing and generation, and references to input data sources.
- A datapackage.json file offering machine-readable information, encompassing name, title, description, license, homepage, author, contributors, and sources.
- A data directory containing the raw data, preferably in a text format like CSV.

Scientific outputs, including journal articles, conference proceedings, and project reports, will be archived in BIA. Data deposited in GitHub, Zenodo, and BIA will remain accessible and reusable beyond the project's lifespan.

4.4.1 Data Licensing

Depending on the type of license, agreements, and protocols adopted by the publisher or data source, certain restrictions on data sharing may apply to collected data. Data generated within the project will be released under an open license (e.g., Creative Commons Zero), allowing for unrestricted use, modification, and sharing as defined by the Open Knowledge Foundation's Open Definition. Specific data licenses will be clearly indicated in both the ReadMe and metadata JSON files accompanying datasets in open repositories.

4.4.2 Data Quality

To facilitate data selection, interpretation, and re-use, data quality will be thoroughly documented. Any potential issues or limitations will be explicitly stated in associated metadata.

5 Costs

All data and scientific findings produced within the project will be openly accessible for sharing and reuse without any limitations. Regarding the collected data, its availability will depend on potential access and reproducibility criteria. Any expenses associated with data management, such as acquisition, deposition, or publication, will be outlined. There are no anticipated costs for maintaining the data beyond the project's duration.

5.1 Data collection

The primary focus of statistical data collection will be on publicly available data, with the possibility of acquiring a few datasets if necessary to comply with the project activities. Each partner is responsible for data purchasing according to the guidelines provided by their national funding agencies. The LCI background data (Ecoinvent) is accessible and already utilized in research initiatives at Eurac's Institute of Renewable Energy, with associated costs covered. There are no anticipated costs for gathering project data, literature, or technical data.

5.2 Data archiving/depositing

The project aims to ensure easy access to research data through various free online repositories: BIA will be utilized for scientific journal articles and other textual documents, GitHub for code files and associated datasets, and Zenodo for output datasets and deliverables. All materials will be prepared by the project partners and reviewed by colleagues, when necessary, without incurring any extra expenses. Therefore, archiving, or depositing data is not anticipated to result in any costs.

5.3 Publishing

All project publications will be released in open access (Green or Gold Licences). Each partner will be responsible for article publishing charges according to the guidelines provided by their national funding agencies and their budget. Public deliverables will be released in open access whereas confidential deliverables will be kept restricted to the Consortium.

6 Data security

To safeguard data integrity, project data will be securely stored on the partners' servers throughout the project's duration and after five years from the project end (01/11/2028). Eurac and the Consortium partners commit to employ cutting-edge technologies for secure data storage, transfer, and user rights management. Data stored on OneDrive or SharePoint is regularly and automatically backed up to ensure data protection.

Depositing the project's generated data and scientific outputs in BIA, GitHub, and Zenodo ensures long-term preservation and curation in accordance with EU guidelines.

7 Ethical and legal aspects

In Eclectic, safeguarding vulnerable groups is a cornerstone. The Consortium will implement robust measures to ensure their data protection, including obtaining explicit consent and providing clear, accessible information about their rights and how their data will be handled in compliance with the GDPR legislation. Special attention will be given to the privacy and dignity of vulnerable participants, with tailored approaches to data collection and storage to mitigate any potential risks. Additionally, strict protocols will be in place to prevent any unauthorized access or misuse of their personal information. A detail description of the protocol is findable in the section 2.1.3.

Eclectic will process personal data, including contact information and professional details of human participants. While it will not actively handle special categories of personal data, such as political opinions, there's a possibility such information may arise in certain research activities. To adhere to data minimization principles, research protocols will be designed to collect only necessary personal data. This data will be stored in identifiable format only for as long as needed for research tasks and according to participants' preferences, with clear explanations provided. Interviewees will receive transparent information about the processing of their personal data, including how and why it's processed, and how to access or correct it, all outlined in the informed consent materials.

The project researchers are aware of the increasingly prominent role of Artificial Intelligence (AI) within research projects. For this reason, the research consortium decided to point out when AI software will be used in the outputs produced. In particular, the name of the software used, and a description of the activities performed by the software will be highlighted. For example,

To write this Data Management Plan ChatGPT3.5 has been used. To rephrase some sentences in English and to translate some sentences from Italian to English.

8 Conclusions

This Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the strategies and steps to ensure transparency, accessibility, reusability, and exploitation of research data linked with the Eclectic project. It is designed to be a dynamic and open document, allowing for further details to be specified and shared as the project unfolds. Consequently, the DMP will undergo revision and updates during the entire life of the project.

9 References

- [1] L. da S. Nascimento and F. K. Steinbruch, "The interviews were transcribed", but how? Reflections on management research', *RAUSP Manag. J.*, vol. 54, no. 4, pp. 413–429, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1108/RAUSP-05-2019-0092.

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